

AWARENESS, ACCESS, AVAILMENT AND SATISFACTION WITH GUIDANCE SERVICES AMONG STUDENTS: BASIS FOR AN ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to determine the awareness, access to, availment, and satisfaction with the guidance services among 361 randomly selected students in a university for the School Year 2018 – 2019. Descriptive study was utilized. It sought to determine relationships between respondents' characteristics such as sex, year level and course to their awareness, access to, and availment of the guidance services. Results revealed that majority of the respondents are aware, have access to, availed and satisfied with the guidance services specifically the assistance rendered by a licensed guidance counsellor, an interview with students to know their concerns, records that provide an overview of personal needs and concerns of every student, and a service that discusses similar concerns with other students and attendance to conferences where students can learn something important. Of the variables considered, year level and course have significant relationship with the awareness, access to, availment, and satisfaction with the guidance services. The respondents were generally female, fourth year, and in the field of Hotel and Restaurant Technology course. Majority of the respondents are aware, have access to, availed and were satisfied with the guidance services.

Keywords: Access, Awareness, Availment, Guidance Services, Satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

Higher Education Institutions must ensure that student affairs and services wherein the Guidance Services is one among them should be utilized by students so that they can attain holistic student development. The study conducted by Ciasico (2016) reported, however, that among the student affairs and services most specifically, the guidance office fell short of expectation among the students. Moreover, because of the lack of personnel as proven by the studies of Cortel (2004) and Villar (2014) effective access and availment of these services may be hindered.

This is especially true to a certain college newly converted into a university status which promotes different guidance programs which are uniquely implemented in the different systems. There is a need, however in a university to have a unified system implementation of these services and assessment of these guidance services must have achieved consistent results and continually improve the process which are duly monitored during accreditation visits. Studies on this subject have been conducted; however, most of them have been conducted in other countries or have focused on two or more variables to which satisfaction has been attributed. It is therefore necessary to conduct this study to contribute towards the improvement of quality guidance services in order to enhance and enrich learning and the total development of students especially in this newly-declared university institution.

METHODOLOGY

Respondents

The study was conducted at the five campuses of Iloilo Science and Technology University, a public institution of higher education located in the Province of Iloilo, Philippines. The subjects were the 361 third year and fourth students, classified according to sex, year level and course drawn using stratified random sampling in combination with cluster sampling from the 3,674 populations of the five campuses during the school year 2018 – 2019.

Data-gathering procedures

The study is a descriptive-relational study that attempted to find out the students' awareness of, access to, availment of and satisfaction with the guidance services in the five campuses of a state university in the Province of Iloilo. The instrument used to gather data was a duly validated and reliable researcher-made questionnaire with a reliability coefficient of 0.83 (Alpha Cronbach). The researcher-made questionnaire was prepared based upon the questionnaire of Villar (2014) and consisted of five parts: Part 1 inquired on the respondent's characteristics, such as sex, year level and course. Part 2 dealt with respondent's awareness of the Guidance Services of the campus. Part 3 looked into the respondent's access to the Guidance Services provided by the school, while Part 4 inquired about the students' availment of the Guidance Services and Part 5 dealt with the respondent's satisfaction with the guidance services. The approval to conduct the study was granted by the head of the institution and the respondents who took part in the study gave consent to have their responses used anonymously in the study. The data about the guidance program of each of the five campuses were collected through personal interview with the Guidance Counsellor and review of certain documents about the school's guidance program during the fielding of the instrument to the students.

Data analyses

The respondents were categorized into the different variables such as, sex (male or female), year level (third year or fourth year) and course (Communication Dev and Food Tech, Education (BEED, BSED and BTTE); Information Tech, Automotive, HRT, and Architecture, and, Agriculture, Agro forestry, Animal Science, and Crop Science). Overall awareness of guidance services refers to the total number of items of guidance and counselling services offered by their respective schools which the respondents were aware of. The total scores obtained by the respondents were categorized into High (14-20), Average (7-13), and Low (0-6). The student's level of availment and satisfaction with the services were determined using the mean scores obtained for each group of indicators and categorized as follows: 4.21 – 5.00- Highly Availment/ Satisfied; 3.41 – 4.20- Mostly Availment/ Satisfied; 2.61 – 3.40 - Moderately Availment/ Somewhat Satisfied; 1.81 – 2.60- Sometimes Availment/ Dissatisfied; and, 1.00 – 1.80 - Poorly Availment/ Very Dissatisfied.

Descriptive statistics used were frequency distribution, means and standard deviation. Inferential statistics employed to ascertain the relationship between variables were Chi-square, Cramer's V, and Pearson r.

RESULTS

The five campuses of the state university under study have existing guidance programs which deliver services according to the provisions of the enhanced CHED Memo No. 9 series of 2013 and those specified in Villar's Comprehensive Guidance Program of 2014 (Villar 2014) which address personal, social academic and career concerns of the students. The services provided are: Information, Individual inventory, Counselling, Placement/Career, Testing, Follow-Up, and Research and Evaluation which are considered vital to the development of well-functioning individuals in order for them to utilize their full potentials (Table 1).

They have a licensed full-time Guidance Counsellor but are given non-guidance tasks such as accomplishing the ISO quality forms, ISO procedures, and are given accreditation assignments and community work as part of their extension services and their offices have the amenities to the clients such as the counselling room, psychometrician's room, researchers' room, consultant's room, secretary's room, and the like.

Table 1: The existing guidance and counselling centre in the five campuses

Services Provided	La Paz	Miagao	Leon	Barotac	Dumangas
A. Guidance Program	√	√	√	√	√
B. Guidance Services	√	√	√	√	√
Information	√	√	√	√	√
Individual inventory	√	√	√	√	√
Counseling	√	√	√	√	√
Placement/career	√	√	√	√	√
Testing	√	√	√	√	√
Follow – up	√	√	√	√	√
Research and Evaluation	√	√	√	√	√
C. Guidance Personnel					
Guidance Coordinator	√	x	x	X	x
Guidance Counselor	√	√	√	√	√
Secretary	x	√	x	X	x
D. Guidance Facilities					
Counseling Room	√	√	√	√	√
Testing Room	x	√	x	X	x
Receiving/Waiting Room	√	√	√	√	√
E. Guidance Budget	√	√	√	√	√
F. Non-guidance Work/Others					
Extension work	√	√	√	√	√
Community Work	√	√	√	√	√
reparation for ISO Survey	√	√	√	√	√
Preparation for Accreditation	√	√	√	√	√

In terms of personal details (Table 2) majority of the respondents were females (58.2 %); slightly more fourth year (53.7%) than third year college (46.3%) and majority belonged to Information Technology, Automotive, HRT, and Architecture courses (55.6%).

Table 2: Distribution of the respondents according to sex, year level, and course.

Category	f	%
Sex		
Male	151	41.8
Female	210	58.2
Total	361	100
Year Level		
Third Year	167	46.3
Fourth Year	194	53.7
Total	361	100
Course		
Communication Dev. and Food Tech	41	11.3
Education (BEED, BSED and BTTE)	87	24.1
Information Tech, Automotive, HRT, and Architecture	175	55.6
Agriculture, Agroforestry, Animal Science, and Crop Science	58	16
Total	361	100

The majority of the respondents were aware of their respective school's guidance and counselling program such as: assistance rendered by a licensed guidance counsellor, an interview with students to know their concerns, records that provide an overview of personal needs and concerns of every student, a service that discusses similar concerns with other students, and attendance to conferences where students can learn something important. Counselling service was the most accessed service by the students; the top three most availed guidance services are: an interview with students to know their concerns, a workshop that enlightens the students' related concerns and a counselling session that focuses on students' difficulties (Table 3). The top three services that students were satisfied are: acquainting the students with training present in the curricular and co-curricular programs, a counselling session that focuses on difficulties, assistance rendered by a licensed guidance counsellor and a service that discusses similar concerns with other students. (Table 4).

Table 3. Respondents' awareness of, access to, availment of guidance services areas.

Guidance Services	Awareness		Access		Availment	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Individual Inventory						
Records of every students'	313	86.7	291	80.6	234	64.8
Records that indicate the student's mental ability	254	70.4	234	64.8	224	62.1
An interview record of students concerns	316	87.5	305	84.5	282	78.1
Information						
A service that conducts training	252	69.8	221	61.2	185	51.2
An activity that highlights one's potentials	228	63.2	227	62.9	185	51.2
Group activities that provide students' experiences	221	61.2	203	56.2	177	49
Acquainting the students with co-curricular programs	299	82.8	282	78.1	241	66.8
Counseling						
Assistance rendered by a counselor	331	91.7	280	77.6	224	62.1
A service that discusses concerns of students	309	85.6	256	70.9	256	70.9
A counseling session that focuses on difficulties	239	66.2	305	84.5	271	75.1
Consultation						
A service to adjust their teaching-learning styles	273	75.6	255	70.6	199	55.1
A classroom activity to decide on the topic to be Discussed	252	69.8	264	73.1	230	63.7
Attendance to conferences where students	309	85.6	277	76.7	246	68.1
Placement						
A service assisting the student to decide on what to do after graduation	267	74	265	73.4	227	62.9
An activity wherein the students are placed in an appropriate educational setting	262	72.6	254	70.4	222	61.5
An activity wherein students are trained in different areas such as resume writing, power dressing and interview	260	72	258	71.5	189	52.4
Follow-up						
A service that determines employed/unemployed graduates	264	73.1	239	66.2	199	55.1
An assistance rendered to students or their family Members	209	57.9	207	57.3	232	64.3
A workshop that enlightens the students' related concerns.	270	74.8	255	70.6	277	76.7
Research and Evaluation						
An activity that evaluates the guidance programs	292	80.9	273	75.6	232	64.3

Table 4: Respondents' satisfaction of guidance services areas.

Guidance Services	Dissatisfied	Somewhat Satisfied	Moderately Satisfied	Highly Satisfied	Mean Score
	%	%	%	%	
Individual Inventory					
Records that provide an overview of personal needs and concerns of every students	0.8	21.8	38.5	38.9	3.66 (S)
Records that indicate the student's mental ability, aptitudes, and special strengths	9.7	27.9	33.2	29.2	3.58 (S)
A recorded interview with students to know their problems	8	23.9	35.3	32.8	3.37 (S)
Information					
A service that conducts training to prepare the student when he/she leaves school.	4.7	27.8	33.2	34.3	3.88 (S)
Group activities that provide students' experiences aside from the day-to-day learning activities	2.2	29	42	26.8	3.45 (S)
Acquainting the students with training present in the curricular and co-curricular programs	5.4	24.5	37.3	33.6	4.08 (S)
Counseling					
Assistance rendered by a licensed guidance	3.3	20.3	33.9	33.3	4.04 (S)
A service that discusses similar concerns with other students	6.9	28.2	34.5	30.4	4.02 (S)
A counseling session that focuses on the difficulties of the student.	9.1	30.4	29.1	31.3	3.48 (S)
Consultation					
A service that assists the students to adjust their teaching-learning styles	2.4	33.5	34.5	29.6	3.76 (S)
A classroom activity wherein the students are free to decide on the topic to be discussed	8.1	23.8	36.9	31.2	3.75 (S)
Attendance to conferences where students can learn something important	8.5	25.5	36.7	29.4	3.50 (S)
Placement					
A service assisting the student to decide on what to	2.4	27.4	40.2	30	3.79 (S)
An activity wherein the students are placed in an appropriate educational setting	6.9	24.4	39.3	29.4	3.73 (S)

An activity wherein students are trained in different areas such as resume writing, power dressing etc.	4.9	17.4	31.3	46.4	3.94 (S)
Follow-up	0				
A service that determines employed/unemployed graduates of the university	1.1	22.8	40.4	35.8	3.82 (S)
An assistance rendered to students or their family members	2.1	22.8	37	38.1	3.41 (S)
A workshop that enlightens the students' related concerns.	6	25.9	41.9	26.8	3.74 (S)
Research and Evaluation					
An activity that evaluates the guidance programs	9.9	21.3	29.5	39.4	3.73 (S)
OVER – ALL SATTISFACTION					3.80 (S)

When the relationship between the respondents' characteristics such as sex, year level and course and their awareness of, access to, availment of and satisfaction of guidance services, the test of association between course and awareness of, year level and course and access to, year level and course and availment of, and course and satisfaction of guidance services were all significant as supported by their respective chi square, Cramer's V and p values. (Table 5) Respondents belonging to the Teacher Education Program course had the highest level of awareness compared to other courses, third year college students and those belonging to Bachelor of Industrial Technology course had higher percentage of those having high access and availment of these services, and those students from the Teacher Education Program registered the highest proportion of "very high" satisfaction with guidance services.

Table 5: Distribution of respondents according to their characteristics and their awareness of, access of, availment of and satisfaction of guidance services

Awareness	COURSE											
	Teacher Education		BIT		HRT		BSIT		Agricultural		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
High	94	90.38	40	93.02	60	71.42	59	81.94	49	84.48	302	83.65
Average	9	8.65	02	4.65	18	21.42	12	16.66	05	8.62	46	12.74
Low	1	4.96	1	2.32	6	7.14	1	1.38	04	6.89	13	3.60
Total	104	100.0	43	100.0	84	100.0	72	100.0	58	100.0	361	100.0
	X ² = 3.527						p value = 0.000				Significant	
	Cramer's V = .699						p value = 0.000				Significant	
YEAR LEVEL												
Access	Third Year		Fourth Year		Total							
	f	%	F	%	f	%						
High	158	95.0	164	85.0	322	87.0						
Average	9	05.4	21	11.0	030	10.0						
Low	0	00.0	9	04.6	099	02.5						
Total	167	100.0	194	100.0	361	100.0						

		$X^2 = 9.276$		p value = 0.010		Significant						
		Cramer's V = 0.010				Significant						
Access	COURSE											
	Teacher Education		BIT		HRT		BSIT		Agricultural		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
High	86	83.49	38	88.37	55	65.47	58	80.55	47	79.66	284	78.67
Average	16	15.53	04	9.30	28	33.33	13	18.05	09	15.25	70	19.39
Low	2	0.97	1	2.32	1	1.19	1	1.38	03	5.08	7	1.93
Total	104	100.0	43	100.0	84	100.0	72	100.0	58	100.0	361	100.0
		$X^2 = 163.812$		p value = 0.000		Significant						
		Cramer's V = .674		p value = 0.000		Significant						
Availment			YEAR LEVEL									
			Third Year		Fourth Year		Total					
			f	%	F	%	f	%				
High			111	66.0	109	56.0	220	61.0				
Low			56	34.0	85	44.0	0141	39.0				
Total			167	100.0	194	100.0	361	100.0				
		$X^2 = 3.986$		p value = 0.046		Significant						
		Cramer's V = 0.046		Significant								
Availmen t	COURSE											
	Teacher Education		BIT		HRT		BSIT		Agricultural		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
High	70	67.30	36	83.72	55	65.47	59	81.94	35	60.34	255	70.64
Low	34	32.69	77	16.27	29	34.52	13	18.05	23	39.65	106	29.36
Total	104	100.0	43	100.0	84	100.0	72	100.0	58	100.0	361	100.0
		$X^2 = 142.531$		p value = 0.000		Significant						
		Cramer's V = 0.628		p value = 0.000		Significant						
Satisfacti on	COURSE											
	Teacher Education		BIT		HRT		BSIT		Agricultural		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Very Satisfied	57	54.80	19	44.18	24	28.57	27	37.50	15	25.86	142	39.33
Moderately Satisfied	31	29.80	9	20.93	31	36.90	19	12.50	23	39.65	113	31.30
Somewhat Satisfied	13	12.50	8	18.60	24	28.57	10	4.16	13	22.41	68	18.83
Dissatisfied	2	1.92	6	13.95	2	2.38	3	4.16	5	8.62	18	4.98
Very Dissatisfied	1	0.96	1	2.32	3	3.57	13	18.05	2	3.44	20	5.54
Total	104	100.0	43	100.0	84	100.0	72	100.0	58	100.0	361	100.0
		$X^2 = 72.789$		p value = 0.012		Significant						
		Cramer's V = 0.234		p value = 0.012		Significant						

When the relationship between the respondents' awareness of, access to, availment of and their satisfaction of the guidance services in their school, the test of relationship revealed a significant relationship between their awareness and availment and satisfaction of guidance services while between access to and their satisfaction of guidance services revealed a not significant relationship (Table 6). Respondents who have high level of awareness of and have availed of the guidance services are definitely satisfied with these services and programs offered in the university. However, whether the respondents may or may not have accessed these services, they are more likely to have satisfaction with the guidance services in the university.

Table 6: Distribution of respondents according to their awareness, access, availment and satisfaction of the guidance services in their school.

Awareness	Satisfaction											
	High Satisfied		Moderately Satisfied		Somewhat Satisfied		Dissatisfied		Very Dissatisfied		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
High	236	74.9	45	14.3	20	6.3	10	03.2	4	1.3	315	87.4
Average	21	58.3	6	16.7	7	19.4	01	02.8	1	2.8	36	9.9
Low	7	70.0	3	30.0	0	0.0	10	0.0	0	0.0	10	2.7
Total	264	73.1	54	15.0	27	7.5	11	3.0	5	1.4	361	100
r = 0.985 p value = 0.020 Significant												
Access												
High	219	74.2	33	11.2	26	8.8	12	4.1	5	1.7	295	81.7
Average	50	76.9	9	13.8	6	9.2	0	0.0	0	0.0	65	18.2
Low	1	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	0.10
Total	269	74.5	55	15.2	37	10.2	12	3.3	5	1.4	361	100
r = 0.096 p value = 0.374 Not Significant												
Availment												
High	94	39.3	58	24.3	49	16.6	28	11.7	10	4.2	239	66.2
Average	30	24.6	57	46.7	25	20.5	66	4.9	4	3.3	122	33.8
Total	124	34.3	115	31.9	74	20.5	34	9.4	14	3.9	361	100
r = 0.949 p value = 0.000 Significant												

DISCUSSION

The present study had clearly proven that there is a guidance office provided for clients in need and a licensed guidance counselor implementing the programs and services offered in the office in all five campuses of the newly-converted state university in the Philippines. Majority of the students are aware of, have access to, and availed of the guidance services specifically the assistance rendered by a licensed guidance counselor, an interview with students to know their concerns, records that provide an overview of personal needs and concerns of every student, and a service that discusses similar concerns with other students and attendance to conferences

where students can learn something important. The services like an activity acquainting students with training present in the curricular and co-curricular programs, assistance rendered by a licensed guidance counselor, an activity wherein students are trained in different areas such as resume writing, power dressing, etc., and a service that conducts training to prepare the student when he/she leaves school are the top five guidance services offered in the university that students are satisfied with. This result is supported by the finding of several studies that revealed that majority of their respondents were aware of the services offered in the guidance office (Tiego 2015; Lasode 2017).

Taken together, the results of the study that revealed that the respondents' course is found to be significantly related to their awareness of the guidance services; their year level and course to their access to guidance services; their year level and course to their availment of guidance services, and their course to their satisfaction with the guidance services is supported by the theory of individual differences upholding a belief that all people are different from all others. It may be viewed that other clients who came from different courses may have different levels of awareness with the guidance services. Moreover, the result that indicated that the access of the guidance services is related to the year level of the respondents whether it may be third year or fourth year college students do not support the theory of Fred Luthans (2008) on Contingency approach that clients' expectations are highly individualized by year level. Higher year level clients may tend to have higher access of the services than the lower year level because they are more responsible and reliable. However, the result that the respondents' course and their availment of the guidance services have significant relationship is supported by Luthans (2008) that clients' expectation is highly individualized by course. It means that the extent of availment of their guidance services would depend whether they came from any degree offered in a certain university.

The respondents' awareness of guidance services is significantly related to their access to these guidance services. Seemingly, their access to guidance services is significantly related to their availment of these programs and services and their awareness and availment of guidance services are significantly related with satisfaction of the guidance services. Thus, respondents who have high level of awareness of the guidance services are definitely satisfied with these services and programs offered in the university. Hence, those respondents who have high awareness of the guidance services in the university are more likely to be definitely satisfied with the presence of such programs and services in the university. Likewise, respondents who have accessed the guidance services are more likely to have satisfaction with these services in the university. The respondents who have availed the guidance services have also high satisfaction with these services. This result is in consonance with the findings of the study of Bedia (2012) which showed significant relationship between respondents' level of awareness to their level of satisfaction of the guidance services in a certain university. Moreover, the relationship between the respondents' availment and satisfaction of the guidance services show that regardless of their availment of the guidance services, they still had a satisfaction of the guidance services. This result is in consonance with the results of the study of Pelaez (2001) and Java (2015) which revealed that the students' availment and the attached value or importance they have given to these student services are related. A student who had availed of these services tended to have attached a greater value and satisfaction offered by the guidance

office. Furthermore, Stipak's (2001) study on satisfaction with urban services had pointed out that the clients can also be more satisfied if they availed or utilized these services provided by the institution. Since clients are recipients of these services, they have knowledge on how these services are accessible to them.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of this study the following conclusions were drawn. Guidance offices were air-conditioned but small to accommodate students.

Guidance counsellors were full-time and licensed, friendly and accommodating, and were given non-guidance responsibilities. The respondents were generally female, fourth year, and in the field of Hotel and Restaurant Technology course. Majority of the respondents are aware, have access to, and availed the guidance services specifically the assistance rendered by a licensed guidance counsellor, an interview with students to know their concerns, records that provide an overview of personal needs and concerns of every student, and a service that discusses similar concerns with other students and attendance to conferences where students can learn something important.

The services like an activity wherein students are trained in different areas such as resume writing, power dressing and interview skills, an activity that evaluates the guidance programs, assistance rendered by a licensed guidance counselor and records that provide an overview of personal needs and concerns of every students and a service that assists the students to adjust their teaching-learning styles are the top five guidance services offered in the university that students are satisfied with.

The respondents' course is found to be significantly related to their awareness of the guidance services while their sex and year level are not significantly related to their awareness. Hence, one's course is a determinant of one's awareness of guidance services. The respondents' year level and course are found to be significantly related to their access to guidance services while their sex is not significantly related to their access to these guidance services. Hence, ones' year level and course are determinants of one's access to the guidance services. The respondents' year level and course are found to be significantly related to their availment of guidance services while their sex is not significantly related to their availment of these guidance services. Hence, ones' year level and course are determinants of one's availment of the guidance services.

The respondents' course is found to be significantly related to their satisfaction with the guidance services while their sex and year level are not significantly related to their satisfaction. Hence, respondents' course is a determinant of one's satisfaction with the guidance services. The respondents' awareness of guidance services is significantly related to their access to these guidance services. One's awareness of guidance services can determine his/her access to these programs and services. The respondents' access to guidance services is significantly related to their availment of these programs and services. Hence, one's access to guidance services is a predictor of his/her availment of these services.

The respondents' awareness and availment of guidance services are significantly related with one's satisfaction of the guidance services while their access to these guidance services are found to be not significantly related with their satisfaction with these services. Hence, ones' awareness and availment is a predictor of his/her satisfaction with guidance services and programs.

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